

Dynamic Burnup with Online Refuelling, Graphite Deformation, and Fuel Salt Off-gassing of the Saltfoss seaMSR-100

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ABSTRACT

This paper details a dynamic burnup algorithm for a MSR which incorporates online refuelling, irradiation driven graphite dimensional change, and fuel salt off-gassing of volatile elements. The algorithm was developed in house at Saltfoss Energy as a tool to aid in analysis of the seaMSR-100 core.

To showcase the capabilities of the algorithm, results produced using a demonstration MSR model with interstitial fuel channels around graphite blocks is presented. The results show that a non-uniform refuelling rate is required, and no refuelling is needed for the first 2-3 y due to Pu breeding. From the results on off-gassing, we see that it improves the fuel economy and removes a sizeable part of the decay power from the fuel. We also see that an interstitial reactor type as modelled here is highly sensitive to the irradiation driven graphite dimensional change, and that it is therefore essential to include these effects in analysis of such a reactor.

Dynamic burnup including graphite dimensional change has been published previously but not including online refuelling and off-gassing.

Keywords: MSR, Serpent, neutronics, fuel cycle, Saltfoss

1. INTRODUCTION

Saltfoss Energy is a nuclear startup based in Copenhagen, Denmark, developing the seaMSR-100 molten salt power reactor.

The seaMSR-100 is designed to be deployed on a floating power plant "power barge", developed in collaboration with Samsung Heavy Industries, KHNP, and Siemens. The power barge is a turn-key power plant that will be mass-produced in the Samsung Heavy Industries shipyard in Korea and towed to the customer. The seaMSR-100 will be produced off-site and inserted into the power barge during the shipyard assembly.

The seaMSR-100 is a loop type – i.e., the fuel salt flows out of the core in the primary loop – LEU fuelled graphite moderated MSR designed for passive safety. In the event of a LOCA, the fuel salt will be drained by gravity into a drain tank where the decay heat is removed by natural convection. See Table for the key parameters of the seaMSR-100.

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Table I *Saltfoss seaMSR-100 overview*

Reactor type	Loop-type MSR
Moderator	Graphite
Intended use	Floating power plant on a barge
Power	250 MWth / 100 MWe (net)
Fuel	FUNaK [1], <2% enrichment
Lifetime	24 y at full power
Refuelling	Online with 5% FUNaK

This paper details a dynamic burnup method used to assess a design alternative of the Saltfoss Energy seaMSR-100 core. This core design alternative is composed of hexagonal vertical graphite blocks, with the interstices serving as the fuel channels. A well-known feature of graphite moderated cores is the graphite dimensional change taking place under of neutron irradiation [2]. A core with interstitial fuel channels is particularly sensitive to this, as a small percentage change in the size of the graphite block, can lead to a large percentage change in the width of the interstices, thereby changing the moderator to fuel ratio, as seen in Figure 1.

Since a change in the moderator to fuel ratio leads to a change in the neutronics of the core and thus the depletion of the fuel, a method of calculating the fuel depletion over the life of the core was needed, which could capture the feedback between the neutronics of the changing core geometry and the fuel depletion. Additionally, online refuelling of – and off-gassing from – the fuel salt needs to be included dynamically as this affects the spectrum and thus the depletion.

To showcase the capability of the dynamic burnup algorithm, a simple core model was used. See Table for the parameters used in this core model.

Table II *Parameters of the design alternative used in this paper.*

Note that the specific parameters shown here are a model to showcase the dynamic burnup algorithm, and are not indicative of the actual Saltfoss seaMSR-100 core design.

Lattice	Hexagonal with interstitial fuel channels
Moderator to fuel ratio	23
Active core radius	240 cm
Active core height	480 cm
Reflector thickness	42 cm
Enrichment	1.9%
Fuel temperature	900 K

Fuel circulation time	60 s
Core lifetime	12 y
Nuclear XS library	ENDF7.1

Figure 1 *Interstitial core lattice. Grey: graphite, red: fuel salt surrounding graphite. Left: Fresh graphite, right: graphite that has shrunk under irradiation, thus expanding the fuel channels. Not to scale.*

2. METHOD

2.1. Dynamic burnup algorithm

The dynamic burnup algorithm subdivides the core lifetime into timesteps. In this example model, a timestep of 3 months was used as a compromise between fidelity and computing time.

The algorithm will start with calculating the correct fuel salt enrichment to be critical at the end of the first timestep, then, in each timestep, the algorithm will:

- Deplete the fuel salt while simulating off-gas and tallying fast neutron flux over different rings of graphite.
- For each graphite region, take the tallied fast flux and multiply with the length of the time step to get the fast fluence. Add to previous fast fluence value for that region to get the cumulative fast fluence.
- Use the cumulative fast fluence for each graphite region to calculate the graphite dimensional change of each region and use this to construct a new geometrical model of the core.
- Using an analytical model, calculate a guess for the refuelling volume needed. Using the new geometrical model, simulate different refuelling volumes by changing the fuel salt composition, deplete for the next timestep and determine by interpolation the correct refuelling volume to be critical at the end of the next timestep.
- Go to next timestep.

A neutronics solver is needed to calculate k-eff and perform fuel depletion, the remainder of the algorithm uses Python. In this case, Serpent 2 [3] was used as the neutronics solver.

To make an initial guess for the refuelling volume required after each burnstep, we can use a simple analytical model for refuelling:

$$V_0 \cdot E_0 + V_r \cdot E_r = V_1 \cdot E_1 \quad (1)$$

Where V_0 and E_0 is the fuel volume and enrichment before refuelling, V_1 and E_1 is the fuel volume and enrichment after refuelling, and V_r and E_r is the refuelling volume and enrichment. The latter, E_r , is set to 5% in this model. Isolating the refuelling volume, and using $V_1 = V_0 + V_r$, we get:

$$V_r = V_0 \cdot \frac{E_1 - E_0}{E_r - E_1} \quad (2)$$

A good guess for E_1 is the enrichment at the beginning of this burnstep. $E_1 - E_0$ is then the depletion of enrichment during the burnstep. As this will – considering only the depletion – be proportional to the inverse of the fuel volume V_0 , we see that the dependency on V_0 disappears from this simplified model to calculate the initial guess of the refuelling volume.

The algorithm is in some respects similar to the one used in [4] but was developed independently. A process diagram of the algorithm can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Process diagram of the dynamic burnup algorithm.

2.1.1. Off-gas modelling

Off-gas of noble gasses and other volatile elements from the fuel salt is modelled using the "mflow" feature [5] in Serpent 2 [3], specifically mode 1 which models continuous off-gassing by incorporating a removal factor into the Bateman equations.

To establish an upper bound on the effect of off-gassing, a removal factor of 99% was chosen, with the time scale of the 60 s fuel circulation time. Thus, the removal constant – analogous to the decay constant – becomes

$$k = -\frac{\ln(1 - 0.99)}{60 \text{ s}} = 0.0768 \frac{1}{\text{s}}$$

2.2. Temperature reactivity coefficients

In a LWR, the fuel is solid and the moderator is liquid. In this MSR model, the fuel is liquid whereas the moderator is solid. Therefore, the relevant temperature reactivity coefficients are:

- Fuel doppler coefficient. This can be quantified by changing the temperature used for doppler processing of the fuel material, and calculating the reactivity change from the baseline.
- Fuel density coefficient. Also known as the fuel void coefficient. This can be quantified by decreasing the fuel density as a temperature increase would [1], and calculating the reactivity change from the baseline.

Both the above temperature reactivity coefficients can thus be expressed in terms of pcm / K.

The temperature interval (ΔT) used to evaluate the reactivity coefficients is 900 – 1000 K. This interval is chosen as a compromise between fidelity and computational cost, as the MC statistics needed for a constant signal to noise ratio scales with $\frac{1}{\Delta T^2}$.

While temperature changes in the graphite will also affect the reactivity, the thermal inertia of the graphite means that these coefficients are of limited relevance to the dynamics of the model investigated here.

3. RESULTS

To showcase the algorithm, 3 dynamic burnups of the model defined in Table II were performed, with 3 different values for the initial fuel volume. From Figure 3 we see that no refuelling is needed for the first 2-3 y, and after that the refuelling volume follows a near-linear 2nd order parabolic as a function of the burn time. While the refuelling volume should not have a dependence on the initial fuel volume if we consider only the depletion, we can see that higher initial fuel volumes means a lower refuelling volume is required. This can be explained by the higher dilution of fission products in a higher fuel volume and improved Pu quality due to lower volume averaged flux over the fuel salt.

The reason why no refuelling is needed over the first few years is a combination of Pu breeding and reduction in the moderator to fuel ratio, going from a very overmoderated core to approaching an optimal moderator to fuel ratio. We can also see the effect of the diminishing moderator to fuel ratio in the fuel density temperature reactivity coefficient: While an overmoderated core gives a negative fuel density coefficients, reducing the moderating to fuel ratio to the optimal will increase the fuel density coefficients to 0. Continuing into an undermoderated regime would result in positive fuel density coefficients and is thus one factor limiting the lifetime of such a core. It should be stated that a part of the increase in the fuel density coefficient is due to changes in the fuel salt composition, specifically the accumulation of Pu240.

Looking at the fast fluence of the individual graphite blocks, we see that all the blocks are well below the turnaround point, and that dimensional change in this fluence range is fairly insensitive to the graphite temperature. Effective cooling of the graphite is still a priority, as the graphite structural probability of failure is sensitive to the temperature.

Figure 3 Top left: Refuelling volume dependence on the initial fuel volume as a function of burntime. Lines through datapoints are 2nd order polynomial fits. Top right: Enrichment and moderator to fuel ratio as a function of burntime for the 42 m³ initial fuel volume. Middle left: Isotopic distribution of fission vs. burntime.

Middle right: Fuel temperature reactivity coefficients vs. burntime. Bottom left: 12 year fast fluence on each graphite column. Bottom right: Graphite dimensional change as function of fluence and temperature [6].

To understand the effect of the off-gassing modelled in the dynamic burnup algorithm, a dynamic burnup with the off-gassing disabled was performed. From Figure 4 we see that off-gassing has a small but significant effect on the required refuelling volume. We also see a significant effect on the decay power in the fuel salt, as a large fraction of the decay power is moved to the off-gas. Note also the slight reduction in decay power over the first ca. 6 years, explained by the increased fraction of Pu239 fission which creates less short-term decay power than U235 fission. It was not possible to measure a statistically significant change in the reactivity coefficients from off-gassing.

Figure 4 Left: Required refuelling volume with and without off-gas modelled. Right: Decay power with and without off-gas modelled.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has explained the dynamic burnup algorithm and showcased examples of the results it can produce.

While the model used here – and the results it has produced – is for demonstration purposes only, it still shows how significant an impact on the neutronics the graphite dimensional change can have for at reactor of this type, and why an analysis like the one presented here is essential.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Fache, "Thermophysical Properties of FUNaK (NaF-KF-UF₄) Eutectics," *Materials*, no. 11, p. 2776, 2024.
- [2] T. D. Burchell, "The effect of neutron irradiation damage on the properties of grade NBG-10 graphite," *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 371, no. 1-3, pp. 18-27, 2007.

- [3] J. Leppänen, "Status of the Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024," *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.*, vol. 11, 2025.
- [4] Y. Zhong, "Neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupled analysis on dimensional change and lifespan of graphite components in small modular molten salt reactor," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 425, 2024.
- [5] L. Seifert, "Material Flows and On-line Reprocessing in Serpent," in *Material Flows and On-line Reprocessing in Serpent*, Munich, 2020.
- [6] A. A. C. a. Y. Katoh, "Report on Effects of Irradiation on Material IG-110," ORNL, Oak Ridge, 2017.